

Information Seeking Behavior of Breast Cancer Patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital, (DESUTH), Oghara, Delta State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the information-seeking behavior of breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital (DELSUTH), Oghara, Delta State, Nigeria. The total population for the study comprised 43 breast cancer patients who were present on a breast cancer clinic day at Delta State Teaching Hospital (DELSUTH) in Oghara, Delta State, Nigeria. The entire population was used as sample using the total enumeration sampling technique. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire. The data collected for this study were analyzed using frequency count and percentage. The study found that breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital needs information on symptoms of breast cancer, the prognosis/causes of breast cancer, the diagnosis of breast cancer, the expected side effect of breast cancer, the treatment and management of breast cancer etc.. They get the information they need from formal sources such as health professionals, family/friends and the Internet. Also, breast cancer patients use the information they get to know breast cancer treatment, understand chemotherapy and its side effects, to support themselves etc. And they face challenges such as limited interaction time with doctors, insufficient information from healthcare providers, and poor understanding of medical terminologies while seeking information. The study recommends that the number of doctors/specialists assigned to breast cancer patients be increased by the management of Delta State University Teaching Hospital as this will reduced the ratio of patients to doctors and afford them better time to communicate and discuss with patients among others.

Keywords: Information Seeking, Information Behaviour, Breast Cancer, Cancer Patients, Delta State University, Teaching Hospital.

Introduction

An increasing amount of research indicates that patients who take an active role in their healthcare tend to experience better health outcomes and lower medical expenses compared to those who are less engaged (Hibbard, 2017). When faced with a serious illness, many patients and their families actively seek information about the condition and its effects on their lives (Treadgold et al., 2020;

Ebel et al., 2017). This is particularly true for breast cancer patients, who often have diverse information needs (Abi Nader et al., 2016; Abu Sharour et al., 2020; Germeni & Schulz, 2014). After receiving a breast cancer diagnosis, patients require information and guidance to help them navigate the condition and its associated challenges. According to Longo et al. (2009, p. 1), breast cancer is the most common cancer among women globally, with the highest incidence rates in North America. In the United States, it is the most frequently diagnosed non-skin cancer and ranks second only to lung cancer as the leading cause of cancer-related deaths in women, with approximately 200,000 new cases reported annually (Longo et al., 2009). Seeking information plays a crucial role in the lives of breast cancer patients and can have lasting effects. Research findings suggest that information-seeking behaviors influence health outcomes (Katavic et al., 2016; Kostagiolas et al., 2020).

Breast cancer information-seeking behavior refers to how individuals search for and utilize information about the disease in different situations. It encompasses both the process of obtaining information and the reasons behind seeking and using breast cancer-related knowledge. Women diagnosed with breast cancer often face significant uncertainties about their health, prompting them to seek information to address their concerns. One way to manage and cope with these uncertainties is by actively searching for breast cancer-related information from various sources, including doctors, the Internet, media, support groups, and, to a lesser extent, cancer information services (CISs) available in some hospitals (Reifegerste et al., 2023). Jensen et al. (2023) reported that approximately 30% of cancer patients do not actively seek information about their condition. They further noted that many patients either lack interest or deliberately avoid illness-related information. Similarly, in a large study of cancer patients, Loiselle (2019) found that nearly 40% were disinterested in or intentionally avoided such information, a trend that can have harmful consequences, including premature deaths, particularly among breast cancer patients.

Breast cancer is among the most frequently searched health topics on the internet. However, there have been relatively few assessments of the quality, accuracy, or usefulness of online breast cancer information (Longo et al., 2009). With physicians no longer being the sole source of health information, it is important to examine how breast cancer patients seek information, the order in which they consult different sources, how they utilize the information, and the challenges they face in the process. In light of this, the present study aims to explore the information-seeking behavior of breast cancer patients at Delta State University Teaching Hospital (DELSUTH), Oghara.

Statement of the Problem

Cancer diagnosis and treatment pose significant challenges, necessitating the acquisition of accurate and timely information to make informed decisions about their healthcare. However, there is a dearth of research investigating the specific information needs, preferences, and behaviors of breast cancer patients in Nigerian hospitals, and university teaching hospitals to be specific. Without a comprehensive understanding of the information-seeking behavior of breast cancer patients, healthcare providers, hospital administrators, and management face difficulties in designing and implementing effective support systems and resources to meet the unique informational requirements of these patients. The effect of the aforementioned is the absence of tailored information delivery mechanisms which may lead to patients experiencing increased anxiety, reduced satisfaction with their healthcare experience, and potentially compromised

treatment outcomes which can lead to the mass death of breast cancer patients. Hence this study examines the information-seeking behavior of breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital (DESUTH), Oghara to fill this gap.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study is to examine the information-seeking behavior of breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital (DELSUTH), Oghara. Specifically, the study is aimed at:

1. identify the information needs of breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital;
2. examine the sources through which breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital access information;
3. identify the purpose for which breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital use the information they get; and
4. investigate the challenges of information seeking among breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study.

1. What are the information needs of breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital, Oghara, Delta State, Nigeria?
2. What are the sources through which breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital access information?
3. What are the purposes for which breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital use the information they get?
4. What are the challenges of information seeking among breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital?

Literature Review

The literature in this study were reviewed in line with the study's research questions.

Information Needs of Breast Cancer Patients

Cancer is a disease characterized by the uncontrolled growth and division of abnormal cells in the body, making it a leading cause of illness and death in both developed and developing countries (Gedefaw et al., 2020). The rising prevalence of this non-communicable disease has become a major concern for healthcare systems. In past decades, national and international public health agencies have primarily focused on controlling infectious and tropical diseases in developing nations. However, according to a 2016 WHO projection, the global cancer burden is expected to rise to 24 million new cases, with 14.6 million cancer-related deaths by 2035. Notably, around 70% of these cases will occur in developing countries (Gedefaw et al., 2020). This growing burden

has heightened the need for information, particularly among breast cancer patients in developing nations like Nigeria.

Discussing the information needs of breast cancer patients and their caregivers, Chua et al. (2020) highlighted that they require information on the disease itself, prognosis, treatment options, potential side effects and their management, hands-on care techniques, and guidance on navigating the healthcare system. Research from various countries has also demonstrated that cancer patients have extensive information needs for various reasons (Tariman et al., 2014; Sheehy et al., 2018). Patients seek information to help them understand and manage their condition, actively participate in their care, and cope with the emotional and psychological challenges associated with the disease (Bray et al., 2018).

Legese et al. (2020, p.2) identified common information needs among breast cancer patients, including details about the disease, available treatments, side effects, pain management, sexuality, daily activities, and emotional support. Similarly, a systematic review by Tariman et al. (2014) found that prognosis, diagnosis, and treatment options ranked as the top three information priorities for cancer patients. In a study conducted at Cancer Disease Hospital in Lusaka, Zambia, Namushi et al. (2020) found that patients sought information on disease progression, necessary tests, treatment methods, physical and psychosocial needs. Furthermore, Chow et al. (2020) studied information needs among Asian women with breast cancer and discovered that receiving timely details about treatment options and potential side effects was among the top three critical concerns at the time of diagnosis. Likewise, a study in Ireland by Sheehy et al. (2018) found that information needs were highest within the first year of diagnosis and significantly declined afterward.

Sources of Information for Breast Cancer Patients

Cancer patients rely on various sources for information, including leaflets, the Internet, and non-medical personnel. However, the majority prefer health professionals as their primary source of information (Kugbey et al., 2019), highlighting the crucial role healthcare providers play in addressing patients' information needs. A study by Legese et al. (2020) on breast cancer patients at Tikur Anbessa Specialized Hospital found that 67.7% of participants preferred receiving information from healthcare professionals, as they were skeptical about the reliability of online sources.

Similarly, Gedefaw et al. (2020) examined cancer information-seeking behavior among university students in Ethiopia and found that among 254 respondents, 48% preferred health workers as their main source of information, followed by the Internet (27.6%). Other commonly cited sources included family members, friends, and traditional media such as television and radio. In another study on cancer follow-up information needs, Shea-Budgell et al. (2014) found that the most frequently used information source was the Internet (57.4%), followed by healthcare providers (32.6%), brochures or pamphlets (25.1%), and cancer organizations (24.3%). Less frequently mentioned sources included toll-free helplines (0.2%), libraries (4.4%), and complementary or alternative medicine practitioners (4.9%).

Maloney et al. (2015) explored the types of online information that breast cancer patients read and discuss with their doctors, revealing that patients typically accessed information from an average

of 3.76 different sources. The most common sources included cancer organization websites (55.7%), hospital or cancer center websites (54.3%), WebMD (41.4%), and government health websites (41.4%). Additionally, Latifi et al. (2019) studied information sources used by women who had undergone mastectomy for breast cancer. Their findings categorized information sources into three groups: medical sources (physicians, surgeons, and healthcare workers), interpersonal sources (family, relatives, and peers), and media sources (printed materials such as brochures, books, and magazines, as well as electronic media like radio, television, the Internet, and social networks).

Purposes for the Use of Information by Breast Cancer Patients

There is limited research on the long-term quality of life (QOL) of disease-free breast cancer survivors. However, studies suggest that access to relevant and high-quality information enhances self-care, helps patients cope with the disease, improves interactions during and after treatment, reduces anxiety and mood disorders, strengthens communication with family, and contributes to overall well-being after surgery. Legese et al. (2020, p. 278) emphasized that understanding and addressing the information needs of breast cancer patients is essential for improving their quality of life. It also plays a key role in reducing depression and anxiety, enhancing coping mechanisms, and encouraging patients to actively participate in their healthcare management. Furthermore, receiving accurate and timely information about their illness and treatment should be considered a fundamental right of breast cancer patients.

Regarding the purpose of seeking information, Legese et al. (2020) found that breast cancer patients benefit from timely and appropriate information, which enables them to make informed treatment decisions, understand their condition, and develop effective coping strategies. Similarly, Ayalew et al. (2022) noted that cancer patients actively seek information to better understand chemotherapy-related side effects and appropriate responses. According to Akhtari-Zavare et al. (2015), the primary motivations for information-seeking among breast cancer patients include gaining a deeper understanding of their disease, alleviating anxiety, and satisfying their curiosity, whereas physician recommendations were found to be a lesser priority.

Shaffer et al. (2013) also reported that most patients seek information as a means of self-protection and support. They do so to gain control over their situation, better understand medical conversations, and support their emotional well-being. Similarly, Kimiafar et al. (2016) found that breast cancer patients in developing countries actively seek information to expand their knowledge, reduce psychological distress, and satisfy their curiosity about the disease. Maloney et al. (2015) further discovered that breast cancer patients use the information they obtain to make healthcare decisions and engage in discussions with their doctors regarding diagnosis, prognosis, treatment options (both conventional and alternative), and potential side effects.

Challenges of Information Seeking among Cancer Patients

There is no doubt that breast cancer patients are experiencing some difficulties in their effort to access information relating to their health. Ravangard et al. (2020) noted that concerns about the quality of received information from various sources are one of the main barriers; which discourage breast cancer patients to seek information. While deliberating on the factors militating

against breast cancer patient's access to information, Namushi et. al. (2020) conducted a study on the information needs of breast cancer patients at Cancer Disease Hospital Lusaka, Zambia, and found that respondents indicated that the health providers did not have adequate time to attend to patients as a common barrier to accessing information. Respondents also noted that there were few doctors to attend to too many patients; hence they were mindful of the time to talk and ask questions. Thus, most respondents cited limited interaction time with doctors due to high patient volume as a barrier to accessing information, as doctors were too busy.

Furthermore, Akbolat et. al. (2021) conducted a study on a survey of health information seeking by cancer patients indicates some problems over medical explanation and terminology. The study found that the main problems encountered by cancer patients while seeking information include insufficient information from healthcare providers, lack of understanding of medical terminology, and lack of help from healthcare providers to explain the information retrieved. In the same vein, Onwe and Okocha (2019) conducted a study on the health information-seeking behaviour of university students in Nigeria and found that lack of easy access to sources was perceived as the main problem by the majority (74.9%) on the respondents. The lack of time was perceived by 72.8% of the respondents as the second highest ranked. Non-availability of relevant information scored 72.3% while (71.7%) indicated that doctors or healthcare workers are not always around, and lack of awareness of where to find information scored (71.5%).

Methodology

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. The population for this study comprises 43 breast cancer patients who were present on the breast cancer clinic day at Delta State Teaching Hospital (DELSUTH) in Oghara, Delta State, Nigeria. The entire population was used as sample using total enumeration sampling technique due to the manageable size of the population after obtaining ethical clearance and permission from the Nurses on duty. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire. A total of 43 copies of the questionnaire were administered and a total of 36 were duly completed and found useable, therefore there was 84% response rate. The data collected for this study were analyzed using simple percentage/frequency counts.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the information needs of breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital?

Table 1: Information needs of breast cancer patients

<i>S/N</i>	<i>I need information on?</i>	<i>Responses</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
1	Symptoms		
1	Prognosis/Cause of breast Cancer	36	100
2	Diagnosis	36	100
3	Expected Side effects	36	100
4	Treatment and management	36	100
5	Best healthcare facility/hospital for treatment	31	84
6	Treatment modalities	36	100
	Treatment financial implications	36	100
7	Diet	36	100

Table 1 revealed that the 36 (100%) of the respondents unanimously agreed that they need information on symptoms of breast cancer, the prognosis/causes of breast cancer, the diagnosis of breast cancer, the expected side effect of breast cancer, the treatment and management of breast cancer, the treatment modalities, the treatment financial implications as well as the diet for breast cancer. Also, 31(84%) representing majority of the respondents agreed that they also need information on the best healthcare facility/hospital for treatment. This means that breast cancer patients in Delta State Teaching Hospital Oghara need information on symptoms of breast cancer, the prognosis/causes of breast cancer, the diagnosis of breast cancer, the expected side effect of breast cancer, the treatment and management of breast cancer, the treatment modalities, the treatment financial implications, diet for breast cancer as well as the best healthcare facility/hospital for breast cancer treatment.

Research Question 2: What are the sources through which breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital access information?

Table 2: Sources of information for breast cancer patients.

S/N	I get information from?	Agree	Percentage	Disagree	Percentage
1	Health professionals	36	100	00	00
2	Internet	19	53	17	47
3	Television	17	47	19	53
4	Radio	17	47	19	53
5	Family and Friends	21	58	15	42
6	Books	09	25	27	75

Table 2 shows that 36(100%) of the respondents agreed to health professionals as source of information. 21(58%) of them agreed to family and friends while 15(42%) of them disagreed. 19(53%) of them agreed with Internet while 17(47%) of them disagreed. 17(47%) of them agreed with television and radio respectively while 19(53%) of them disagreed. Only 9(25%) of them agreed to books as a source of information while majority 27(75%) of them disagreed. This means that the sources of information for breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital in the top flight is health professionals which was closely followed by family and friends and this was followed by the Internet. However, breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital do not use television, radio and books as sources of information.

Research Question 3: What are the purposes for which breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital use the information they get?

Table 3: Purpose of the use of information by breast cancer patients.

S/N	I use information for?	Responses	Percentage
1	Know about breast cancer treatment	36	100
2	Understand chemotherapy and its side effects	36	100
3	To support myself	36	100
4	understand physician conversations better	36	100

Table 3 revealed that 36(100%) representing all the respondents unanimously agreed that they use information the information they get for the purpose of knowing breast cancer treatment,

understand chemotherapy and its side effects, to support themselves, and to understand physician conversations better. This means that the purpose of the use of information by breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital is to know breast cancer treatment, understand chemotherapy and its side effects, to support themselves, and to understand physician conversations better.

Research Question 4: What are the challenges of information seeking among breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital?

Table 4: Challenges of information seeking among breast cancer patients.

S/N	I encounter the following challenges when seeking information	Responses	Percentage
1	limited interaction time with doctors	36	100
2	insufficient information from healthcare providers	36	100
3	poor understanding of medical terminologies	36	100
4	lack of access to the internet	12	33
5	lack of access to radio	07	19.4
6	lack of access to television	08	22.2
7	lack of awareness of where to find breast cancer information	13	36

Table 4 revealed that 36(100%) indicating all the respondents unanimously agreed that limited interaction time with doctors, insufficient information from healthcare providers, and poor understanding of medical terminologies. However, only 12(33%) of the respondents sees lack of access to the internet as a challenge, only 7(19.4%) of them responded to lack of access to television as a challenge, 8(22.2%) of them responded to lack of access to television as a challenge and 13(36%) of them sees lack of awareness of where to find breast cancer information as a challenge. This means the challenges of information seeking among breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital is limited interaction time with doctors, insufficient information from healthcare providers, and poor understanding of medical terminologies.

Discussion of findings

This study revealed clearly that the information needs information on symptoms of breast cancer, the prognosis/causes of breast cancer, the diagnosis of breast cancer, the expected side effect of breast cancer, the treatment and management of breast cancer, the treatment modalities, the treatment financial implications, diet for breast cancer as well as the best healthcare facility/hospital for breast cancer treatment. This finding agrees with the one by Chua et. al. (2020), that breast cancer patients and their givers need information on the disease, prognosis, treatment, and expected side effects and their management, hands-on care skills, and accessing and navigating the healthcare system, including resources. Also, this study revealed that the sources of information for breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital in the top flight is health professionals which was closely followed by family and friends as well as the Internet. This finding is in line with the one by Gedefaw et. al. (2020), that the study participants preferred health workers as their primary source of cancer information while the Internet is their second choice.

This study further uncovered that the purpose of the use of information by breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital is to know breast cancer treatment, understand chemotherapy and its side effects, to support themselves, and to understand physician conversations better. This finding concurs with the findings of researchers such as Legese et. al. (2020); Ayalew et.al (2022); and Shaffer et. al. (2013) who respectively found that to learn about the disease, and control their life and coping mechanism; to understand chemotherapy-related adverse effects and actions to be taken found and to protect and support themselves are the major purpose for which cancer patients use the information they get. Also, this study vividly revealed that the challenges of information seeking among breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital is limited interaction time with doctors, insufficient information from healthcare providers, and poor understanding of medical terminologies. This finding agrees with that of Namushi et. al. (2020) who found that respondents indicated that the barriers to their information access is that the health providers did not have adequate time to attend to patients. To further corroborate the finding, Akbolat et. al. (2021) found that the main problems encountered by cancer patients while seeking information include insufficient information from healthcare providers, lack of understanding of medical terminology, and lack of help from healthcare providers to explain the information retrieved.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined information-seeking behavior of breast cancer patients in Delta State Teaching Hospital (DELSUTH), Oghara. It is safe to conclude from this study that breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital needs information on symptoms of breast cancer, the prognosis/causes of breast cancer, the diagnosis of breast cancer, the expected side effect of breast cancer, the treatment and management of breast cancer, the treatment modalities, the treatment financial implications, diet for breast cancer as well as the best healthcare facility/hospital for breast cancer treatment. The breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital get their information mainly from health professionals, family/friends and the Internet. The breast cancer patients use the information they get to know breast cancer treatment, understand chemotherapy and its side effects, to support themselves, and to understand physician conversations better. Breast cancer patients in Delta State University Teaching Hospital face some challenges in their efforts to seek for information and some of them are: limited interaction time with doctors, insufficient information from healthcare providers, and poor understanding of medical terminologies. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommends that:

1. The numbers of doctors/specialist assigned to breast cancer patients should be increased by the management of Delta State University Teaching Hospital as this will reduced the ratio of patients to doctor and afford them better time to communicate and discuss with patients.
2. Sufficient time should be allotted to each breast cancer patients to discuss with their doctors as the patients see their doctors as their best sources of information.
3. The Delta State University Teaching Hospital management should develop other means of sharing breast cancer information to their patients and this can include printing of fliers, poster etc.

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